

EFFECT OF THE FABRICATION PROCESS ON THE PROPERTIES OF PITCH-BASED CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Short carbon fiber reinforced pitch-based carbon-carbon composites (SCFRCs) were fabricated under atmospheric environment using the mould pressing and semi-carbonization shaping technology. The effect of the molding pressure and molding temperature on the density and the mechanical properties of the SCFRCs was studied in detail.

Keywords: pitch-based carbon-carbon composites, short carbon fiber, mechanical properties, fabrication process

INTRODUCTION

Short carbon fibre reinforced carbon-carbon composites (short for SCFRCs) exhibit wider prospect application than continuous carbon fibre reinforced composites due to its rich raw materials, simple molding technologies and low producing cost. However, lower mechanical properties are a bottleneck inhibiting the popularization and application of the SCFRCs [1-3]. The fabrication processes, especially for molding pressure and molding temperature, importantly influence the mechanical properties of the SCFRCs. In view of this, the SCFRCs were fabricated under atmospheric environment using the mould pressing and semi-carbonization shaping technology (MSCT) [4] and the influences of molding pressure and molding temperature on the density and the compressive strength were also studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw materials

The major raw materials were calcined pitch coke (provided by Lanzhou Carbon Works) and the coal-tar pitch (provided by Taiyuan Iron & Steel Group) with softening point 260°C. The grain size of the pitch coke and the coal-tar pitch was 40~400 mesh and 70~400 mesh respectively. To remove the organic glue retained at the of the carbon fibers, the 6k PAN based short carbon fiber with 6-8µm filament diameter was heat-treated at 1100°C for 2h at nitrogen atmosphere. Then, the dispersion liquid containing 0.5wt% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and 0.2wt% cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB) was employed to disperse the fibers [5].

Preparation method

First, short carbon fibre, binder pitch and pitch coke were weighted and mixed according to the requirement of the orthogonal table $L_9(3^4)$. The weight percent of the short carbon fibre and binder was 2.5% and 33%, respectively. The residual was pitch coke. Then, the ingredients mixed evenly and dried were poured into the metal mould cavity. The molded samples with the size of $\Phi 120\text{mm} \times 20\text{mm}$ were fabricated using a hydraulic machine by way of MSCCT at atmospheric environment. The molding temperature and molding pressure was designed as 570°C , 600°C , 630°C and 45MPa, 80MPa, 115MPa. At last, the prepared samples were treated successively through quick baking and one time densification (pitch impregnation and carbonization treatment) and the baked samples and densified samples were obtained [6].

Performance test

The prepared SCFRCs were machined into $10\text{mm} \times 10\text{mm} \times 15\text{mm}$ rectangular samples. The volume-weight method was used to measure and calculate the volume density. Then the compressive strength was measured under a ZD 10/90 type electronic universal materials testing machine (the loading direction is parallel to the orientation of the mould pressure). Seven samples of the same type were processed and measured, and the result was the average value.

Structure observation

The selected SCFRCs were observed under a horizontal OLYMPUS-PMG3 optical microscopy after treatment through cutting, coarse grinding, fine grinding and polishing. Meanwhile, the fracture surface of the samples was observed and analyzed under a HITACHI-570 scanning electron microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The influence of molding pressure on the properties of SCFRCs

Fig.1 shows the influence of molding pressure on the density and compressive strength of SCFRCs. It could be found that the molding pressure effects greatly on the density and compressive strength. When the molding pressure increases to 80MPa from 45MPa, the density and compressive strength of the baked samples and densified ones increase greatly; when the molding pressure keeps increasing, the density and compressive strength increases slowly. As the molding pressure increases to 115MPa from 45MPa, the density (compressive strength) of baked samples and densified ones increases by 12.2%(77.8%) and 6.7%(88.6%), respectively.

The density and compressive strength of SCFRCs increase with the molding pressure increasing. This is different with the influence of molding pressure on the compressive strength of pitch based carbon composites (PCCs) [7]. When the molding pressure is more than 80MPa, the compressive strength of SCFRCs increases slowly with molding

pressure increasing continuously but the compressive strength of SCFRCs apparently decreases. The reinforcement effect of short carbon fiber is why that explains this phenomenon. Although the probability of crushing pith coke increases with the molding pressure increasing, the compressive strength of SCFRCs still increases due to the existence of the short carbon fibers.

Fig.1 Effect of molding pressure on the properties of SCFRC

BP—baked samples; DP—Densified samples

The molding pressure impacts directly on the density of SCFRCs because it could enhance the dense degree of the ingredients mixture. So the bigger the molding pressure is, the higher the density of the molded samples is. When the nature and ratio of raw materials and manufacture technology are same, the density and mechanical properties of SCFRCs increase with the molding pressure increasing.

The influence of molding temperature on the properties of SCFRCs

The influence of molding temperature on density and mechanical properties are displayed in Fig.2. When the molding temperature increases to 600°C from 570°C, the density (compressive strength) of baked samples and densified ones increases by 5.8% (38.8%) and 3.5% (49.9%), respectively. When the molding temperature increases continuously, the density and compressive strength drop thereupon. The further investigation show that the density of moulded samples and the molding temperature have direct relationship and the curve between them is in peak shape (Fig.3). After the moulded samples obtained at different temperature are baked at the same condition, the density of them drops to some extent, but the decreased magnitude is smaller. This makes the density of the baked samples and molding temperature keep the same relationship. The compressive strength and densified samples have the familiar relationship. The relationship between the molding temperature and the density of the moulded samples could be interpreted as following: with the influence of molding pressure, the higher the molding temperature is, the more thorough the carbonization of quasi-moulded samples is and the bigger the volume shrinkage is [8]. Therefore, the

density of the moulded samples increased when the molding temperature increases to 600°C from 500°C. When the molding temperature is more than 600°C, the porosity contained in quasi-moulded samples increases and leads the dropping of the density of the moulded samples [9].

Fig.2 Effect of molding temperature on the properties of SCFRC

BP—baked samples; DP—Densified samples

Fig.3 Effect of molding temperature on density of molded samples of SCFRC materials

In addition, it could be seen from Fi.1 and Fig.2 that (1) the relationship between the density and molding pressure (molding temperature) is resemble with the relationship between the compressive strength and molding pressure (molding temperature) no matter what kinds the samples are. This indicates that the compressive strength of SCFRCs have close relationship with the density. The higher the density is the higher compressive strength. In order to improve the mechanical properties of SCFRCs, various procedures should be tried to improve its density; (2) the density and mechanical properties are lower, but they increase greatly after densification. The results are uniform with that of granular coke reinforced pitch based carbon composites [10].

CONCLUSION

(1) The properties of the SCFRCs increase with the molding pressure increasing. When the molding pressure increases to 115MPa from 45MPa, the density (compressive strength) of the baked samples and the densified ones increases by 12.2% (77.8%) and 6.7% (88.6%), respectively.

(2) When the molding temperature increases to 600°C from 570°C, the density (compressive strength) of the baked samples and the densified ones increases by 5.8% (38.8%) and 3.5% (49.9%), respectively. When the molding temperature keeps increasing, the density and compressive strength drop.

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